

Pengelolaan Jurnal OJS 3

Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto

Directed By:

Jurusan Teknik Sipil dan Kebumihan Politeknik Negeri Banjarmasin

Via Zoom, Jumat, 26 November 2021

Profil

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Selayang pandang jurnal

- Sejak tahun 2016 dan terbitnya Permenristekdikti tahun 2017 maka dimulailah perubahan mendasar terkait publikasi ilmiah di Indonesia
- Dari yang tadinya cetak menjadi elektronik
- Dari yang berbasis hasil menjadi proses
- Author berkolaborasi demikian juga pengelolaan jurnal juga berkolaborasi
- Jurnal bisa juga menjadi tolak ukur World Class University
- Peran Jurnal ditentukan oleh editor (reviewer)
- Jurnal ini “ibarat menanam” dibiayai oleh kita tapi author tidak boleh dari dalam semuanya

Memberikan umpan balik ke lembaga

27

JURNAL TERAKREDITASI NASIONAL UIN SUNAN GUNUNG DJATI BANDUNG

Selasa, 11 Oktober 2019

NO	NAMA JURNAL	PENGELOLA	SINTA					
			S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
1	Jurnal Pendidikan Islam	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
2	Jurnal Tadris Kimiya	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
3	Jurnal Analisa	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
4	Jurnal Bioedukin: Program Studi Pendidikan Biologi	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
5	al-Aulad: Journal of Islamic Primary Education	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
6	Athulab: Islamic Religion Teaching and Learning Journal	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
7	Jurnal ISEMA: Islamic Educational Management	Fak. Tarbiyah dan Keguruan						
8	Wawasan: Jurnal Ilmiah Agama dan Sosial Budaya	Fak. Ushuluddin						
9	Religious: Jurnal Studi Agama-Agama dan Lintas Budaya	Fak. Ushuluddin						
10	Al-Bayan: Jurnal Studi Al-Qu'an dan Tafsir	Fak. Ushuluddin						
11	Diroyah: Jurnal Studi Ilmu Hadis	Fak. Ushuluddin						
12	Syifa al-Qulub Takawuf Psikoterapi	Fak. Ushuluddin						
13	Jurnal AGRO	Fak. Sains dan Teknologi						
14	Jurnal Biodjati	Fak. Sains dan Teknologi						
15	JOIN (Jurnal Online Informatika)	Fak. Sains dan Teknologi						
16	TELKA: Jurnal Telekomunikasi, Elektronika, Komputasi dan Kontrol	Fak. Sains dan Teknologi						
17	Al-Kimiya: Jurnal Ilmu kimia dan Terapan	Fak. Sains dan Teknologi						
18	Ilmu Dakwah: Academic Journal for Homiletic Studies	Fak. Dakwah dan Komunikasi						
19	Communicatus: Jurnal Ilmu Komunikaal	Fak. Dakwah dan Komunikasi						
20	Arada (Aktualisasi Nuanza Ilmu Dakwah)	Fak. Dakwah dan Komunikasi						
21	Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik (JISPO)	Fak. Ilmu Sosial dan Politik						
22	TEMALI: Jurnal Pembangunan Sosial	Fak. Ilmu Sosial dan Politik						
23	Paympathic: Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi	Fak. Psikologi						
24	Asy-Syar'ah	Fak. Syariah dan Hukum						
22	ADLIYA: Jurnal Hukum dan Kemanusiaan	Fak. Syariah dan Hukum						
26	Al-Tsaqala : Jurnal Ilmiah Peradaban Islam	Fak. Adab dan Humaniora						
27	International Journal of Nusantara Islam	UIN SGD/Pascasarjana						

Jurnal Ilmiah UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung
Menuju INDONESIA Maju

Busro

4 MENIT YANG LALU

Akreditasi Jurnal

- ▶ Kita bukan Superman
- ▶ Kerja tim
- ▶ Mengerjakan jurnal itu tugas sampingan (Resmawan, 2018)

Sistem Operasional Jurnal

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

1. Ada pemberitahuan apabila artikel masuk atau submit

The screenshot displays the OJS 3 user interface. On the left, a dark sidebar contains navigation menus: 'Submissions' (with sub-items 'Issues' and 'Announcements'), 'Settings' (with sub-items 'Journal', 'Website', 'Workflow', 'Distribution', and 'Users & Roles'), and 'Statistics' (with sub-items 'Articles', 'Editorial Activity', 'Users', and 'Reports'). The main content area is partially obscured by a white modal window titled 'Tasks'. This modal lists two tasks, each with an unchecked checkbox:

- This is a kind reminder for you to check your journal's health through the editorial report.
- A new article has been submitted to which an editor needs to be assigned.
KADAR POLIFENOL TOTAL PADA TEH HIJAU (CAMELLIA SINENSIS) MENGGUNAKAN EKSTRAKSI MASERASI DENGAN PERBANDING

Below the tasks are three buttons: 'Mark New', 'Mark Read', and 'Delete'. At the bottom right of the modal, it indicates '1 - 2 of 2 items'. In the background, a 'New Submission' button is visible, and the top right corner shows a notification bell icon with a red '2' and a user profile icon. The footer of the page includes the text 'Activate Windows'.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

2. Muncul status artikel

The screenshot displays the Pharmademica OJS 3 interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/1`. The page title is "Pharmademica". The breadcrumb trail is "1 / pharmademica / KADAR POLIFENOL TOTAL PADA TEH HIJAU (CAMELLIA SINENSIS) MENGGUNAKAN EKSTRAKSI MASERASI DEN". The page features a navigation menu on the left with categories: Submissions, Issues, Announcements, Settings (Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles), and Statistics (Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports). The main content area has tabs for "Workflow" and "Publication". Under "Publication", there are sub-tabs for "Submission", "Review", "Copyediting", and "Production". A "Help" button is visible. The "Submission Files" section shows a file named "ARTIKEL DWI EVITA, ERNA-dikonversi.docx" with a date of "September 3, 2021" and a status of "Article Text". A "Download All Files" button is present. The "Pre-Review Discussions" section has an "Add discussion" button and a table with columns: Name, From, Last Reply, Replies, and Closed. The table currently shows "No Items". On the right side, there are instructions to "Assign an editor to enable the editorial decisions for this stage.", a "Participants" section with an "Assign" button, and an "Author" section listing "admin pharmademica". A "Library" button is also visible in the top right.

Pharmademica

Submissions 1 / pharmademica / KADAR POLIFENOL TOTAL PADA TEH HIJAU (CAMELLIA SINENSIS) MENGGUNAKAN EKSTRAKSI MASERASI DEN Activity Log Library

Issues

Announcements

Settings

Journal

Website

Workflow

Distribution

Users & Roles

Statistics

Articles

Editorial Activity

Users

Reports

Workflow Publication

Submission Review Copyediting Production Help

Submission Files Search Upload File

ARTIKEL DWI EVITA, ERNA-dikonversi.docx September 3, 2021 Article Text

Download All Files

Pre-Review Discussions Add discussion

Name	From	Last Reply	Replies	Closed
No Items				

Assign an editor to enable the editorial decisions for this stage.

Participants Assign

Author

admin pharmademica

Activate Windows

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

3. Klik Editor dengan klik Assign

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/1`. The main content is a modal dialog titled "Assign Participant" with a "Help" icon and a close button. The dialog is divided into several sections:

- Locate a User:** This section contains a dropdown menu currently set to "Journal editor" and a text input field. Below the input field is the text "Search User By Name". A blue "Search" button is positioned to the right of the input field.
- Name:** A label for the search results, currently showing "No Items".
- Choose a predefined message to use, or fill out the form below:** A dropdown menu for selecting a message.
- Message:** A text area for entering a custom message.

In the background, the "Pharmademica" sidebar is visible on the left, listing various menu items such as "Settings", "Journal", "Website", "Workflow", "Distribution", "Users & Roles", "Statistics", "Articles", "Editorial Activity", "Users", "Reports", and "Tools". On the right side of the background, there is a "Participants" section with an "Assign" button and an "Author" section with a dropdown menu showing "admin pharmademica".

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3 Pharmademica

4. Memasukkan nama editor yang ditunjuk untuk memeriksa artikel

The screenshot shows the 'Assign Participant' dialog box in the Pharmademica OJS 3 interface. The dialog is titled 'Assign Participant' and has a 'Help' icon in the top right corner. It is divided into several sections:

- Locate a User:** This section contains a dropdown menu with 'Journal editor' selected, a search input field with the placeholder text 'Search User By Name', and a 'Search' button.
- Name:** Below the search field, the name 'Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto' is listed with a radio button selected next to it. A '1 of 1 items' indicator is shown at the bottom right of this list.
- Assignment privileges:** This section has a checked checkbox and the text: 'This participant is only allowed to recommend an editorial decision and will require an authorised editor to record editorial decisions.'
- Choose a predefined message to use, or fill out the form below:** A dropdown menu is set to '[[pharm] A message regarding Pharmademica'.
- Message:** A text input field is located at the bottom of the dialog.

The background shows the Pharmademica dashboard with a sidebar menu on the left containing items like Submissions, Issues, Announcements, Settings, Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles, Statistics, Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports, and Tools. The main content area is partially visible, showing 'Activity Log' and 'Library' tabs.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

5. Tertulis nama editor yang ditunjuk

The screenshot displays the Pharmademica OJS 3 interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/1`. The page title is "Pharmademica". The navigation menu on the left includes: Announcements, Settings (Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles), Statistics (Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports), and Tools.

The main content area is titled "Workflow" and "Publication". It features sub-tabs for "Submission", "Review", "Copyediting", and "Production". A "Help" button is visible in the top right of the main content area.

Submission Files

File Name	Count	Article Text
ARTIKEL DWI EVITA, ERNA-dikonversi.docx	3	Article Text

Buttons: Search, Upload File, Download All Files, Send to Review, Accept and Skip Review, Decline Submission.

Pre-Review Discussions

Name	From	Last Reply	Replies	Closed
[jpharm] A message regarding Pharmademica	enursofianto	-	0	<input type="checkbox"/>

Buttons: Add discussion.

Participants (Assign)

Journal editor

- Tri Danang Kurniawan

Author

- admin pharmademica

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

6. Klik Add Discussion

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `journal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/1`. The page title is "PKP pharmademica | KADAR POLIFEN". A modal dialog box titled "Add discussion" is open, featuring a close button (X) in the top right corner. The dialog contains the following sections:

- Participants:** A list of users with checkboxes. "Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto, Unassigned" is selected with a blue checkmark. Other participants are "Tri Danang Kurniawan, Journal editor" and "admin pharmademica, Author".
- Subject *:** A text input field for the discussion subject.
- Message *:** A rich text editor with a toolbar containing icons for undo, redo, bold, italic, underline, link, unlink, code, list, image, and link. Below the toolbar is a large text area for the message content.
- Attached Files:** A section at the bottom with buttons for "Search", "Upload File", and "Select Files".

In the background, the "Pharmademica" sidebar is visible on the left, listing various settings and statistics. On the right, a "Journal editor" panel shows a list of participants with expandable arrows.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

7. Klik komentar dan upload artikel

The screenshot displays the Pharmademica OJS 3 interface. A modal dialog titled "Upload a Discussion File" is open, showing a three-step process: 1. Upload File, 2. Review Details, and 3. Confirm. The "Article Component" field is currently set to "Select article component". Below the field are "Continue" and "Cancel" buttons. The background interface includes a sidebar with navigation options like Settings, Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles, Statistics, Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports, and Tools. The main content area shows "Attached Files" with a "No Files" message and buttons for "Search", "Upload File", and "Select Files". A "Participants" list is visible on the right, including "Journal editor", "Tri Danang Kurniawan", and "admin pharmademica".

Pharmademica | KADAR POLIFEN x +

← → ↻ jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/1 ☆ 📄 🗨️ 🛠️ 👤 ⋮

Upload a Discussion File ×

1. Upload File 2. Review Details 3. Confirm

Article Component *

Select article component

Continue Cancel

Attached Files 🔍 Search Upload File Select Files

No Files

* Denotes required field

OK Cancel

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

8. Upload Komentar Editor

The screenshot displays the OJS 3 interface for editing a message. The browser address bar shows the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/1`. The page title is "Pharmademica".

The main content area is titled "Message *" and contains a rich text editor with the text "Sesuaikan template". The editor toolbar includes icons for undo, redo, bold, italic, underline, link, unlink, source code, list, and image.

Below the message editor is the "Attached Files" section, which includes a search bar and buttons for "Search", "Upload File", and "Select Files". The attached files are listed in a table:

File Name	Size	Count	Content Type
15375-47159-1-RV.doc	2	4	Article Text
15375-47159-1-RV.doc	3	4	Article Text

The right sidebar contains several sections:

- Send to Review** (button)
- Accept and Skip Review** (button)
- Decline Submission** (button)
- Participants** (button) with an **Assign** button
- Journal editor** (list): Tri Danang Kurniawan
- Author** (list): admin pharmademica

The bottom of the page shows a watermark for "Activate Windows" and a link to "Go to Settings to activate Windows."

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

9. Menunggu perbaikan artikel dari author

10. Klik Reviewer

The screenshot displays the Pharmadematica OJS 3 interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: `journal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmadematica/workflow/index/1/3`. The page title is "Pharmadematica". The navigation menu on the left includes: Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles, Statistics, Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports, and Tools. The main content area is titled "Review" and shows the "New Review Round" section. The "Round 1 Status" box indicates "Waiting for reviewers to be assigned." Below this, there are three main sections: "Review Files" (No Files), "Reviewers" (No Items), and "Revisions" (No Files). On the right side, there are buttons for "Request Revisions", "Accept Submission", and "Decline Submission". The "Participants" section lists "Journal editor" and "Author" (Tri Danang Kurniawan). The "Revisions" section has a search and upload file button.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

11. Klik Reviewer

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/3`. The page title is "Pharmademica | KADAR POLIFEN". A modal dialog box titled "Add Reviewer" is open in the center. The dialog has a search bar labeled "Locate a Reviewer" with a search icon and a "Filters" button. Below the search bar, the name "Nasrudin" is displayed, along with a "0" icon and the text "Never assigned". A "Select Reviewer" button is positioned to the right of the name. At the bottom of the dialog, there are two buttons: "Create New Reviewer" and "Enroll Existing User". The background of the page is dimmed, showing a sidebar with navigation options like "Journal", "Website", "Workflow", "Distribution", "Users & Roles", "Statistics", "Articles", "Editorial Activity", "Users", "Reports", and "Tools". The main content area is also dimmed, showing sections for "Review Files", "Reviewers", "Revisions", "Request Revisions", "Accept Submission", "Decline Submission", "Participants", and "Journal editor".

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

12. Kirim artikel dengan batas waktu mengerjakan dan Blind Review

The screenshot shows the submission workflow interface for Pharmademica. The browser address bar displays the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/3`. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options: Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles, Statistics, Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports, and Tools. The main content area contains the following elements:

- Submission URL:** A dropdown menu with the text "URL".
- Thank you for considering this request.**
- Do not send email to Reviewer.
- Important Dates:** Two date input fields, both containing "02-10-2021". The first is labeled "Response Due Date" and the second is labeled "Review Due Date".
- No Files Selected:** A message box stating "You have not selected any files for the reviewer to review." Below this is a button labeled "+ Files To Be Reviewed".
- Review Type:** Three radio button options:
 - Anonymous Reviewer/Anonymous Author
 - Anonymous Reviewer/Disclosed Author
 - Open
- Buttons:** "Add Reviewer" and "Cancel" buttons at the bottom.

On the right side of the interface, there are several action buttons: "Request Revisions", "Accept Submission" (highlighted in dark blue), and "Decline Submission". Below these are "Participants" and "Assign" buttons, and a "Journal editor" section listing "Tri Danang Kurniawan" with an "Assign" button next to it.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

13. Pada artikel ditampilkan status reviewer

The screenshot displays the Pharmadematica OJS 3 interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmadematica/workflow/index/1/3. The page title is "Pharmadematica". The main content area is titled "Round 1" and "New Review Round".

Round 1 Status
Waiting for reviewers to be assigned.

Review Files
No Files

Reviewers
Add Reviewer

Reviewer	Status	Response due	Role
Nasrudin	Request Sent	2021-10-02	Anonymous Reviewer/Anonymous Author

Revisions
No Files

Review Discussions
Add discussion

Request Revisions
Accept Submission
Decline Submission

Participants
Assign

Journal editor
Tri Danang Kurniawan

Author
admin pharmadematica

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

14. Klik keputusan Reviewer

The screenshot displays the OJS 3 interface for a journal named 'Pharmademica'. The browser address bar shows the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/3`. The left sidebar contains navigation menus for 'Settings', 'Statistics', and 'Tools'. The main content area is titled 'Require New Review Round' and features two radio button options: 'Revisions will not be subject to a new round of peer reviews.' (selected) and 'Revisions will be subject to a new round of peer reviews.'. Below this is a 'Send Email' section with two radio button options: 'Send an email notification to the author(s): admin pharmademica' (selected) and 'Do not send an email notification'. A rich text editor is present, containing the text: 'admin pharmademica: We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Pharmademica, "KADAR POLIFENOL TOTAL PADA TEH HIJAU (CAMELLIA SINENSIS) MENGGUNAKAN EKSTRAKSI MASERASI DENGAN PERBANDINGAN PELARUT ETANOL - AIR". Our decision is: Revisions Required'. At the bottom of the editor is a 'Select review files to share with the author(s)' section with 'No Files' listed. The right sidebar shows a 'Help' button and a list of actions: 'Request Revisions', 'Accept Submission' (highlighted in dark blue), 'Decline Submission', 'Participants' with an 'Assign' button, and 'Journal editor' with an 'Assign' button. At the bottom right, there are buttons for 'Record Editorial Decision' and 'Cancel'.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

15. Klik Send To Production

The screenshot displays the Pharmademica OJS 3 workflow interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/3`. The interface features a dark blue header with the 'Pharmademica' logo and navigation icons. A left sidebar contains a menu with categories like 'Issues', 'Announcements', 'Settings', 'Statistics', and 'Tools'. The main content area is divided into 'Workflow' and 'Publication' tabs, with sub-tabs for 'Submission', 'Review', 'Copyediting', and 'Production'. The 'Production' sub-tab is active, showing a 'Draft Files' section with 'No Files', a 'Copyediting Discussions' section with 'No Items', and a 'Copyedited' section with 'No Files'. A prominent blue 'Send To Production' button is visible on the right side of the main content area. Below this button, there are sections for 'Participants' (with an 'Assign' button), 'Journal editor' (listing 'Tri Danang Kurniawan'), and 'Author' (listing 'admin pharmademica'). A watermark 'Activate Windows' is visible at the bottom right of the interface.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

16. Create issue

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/managelIssues`. The page title is "PKP Issues | Pharmademica". The main content area is titled "Issues" and has two tabs: "Future Issues" (active) and "Back Issues". A "Help" button is visible in the top right of the content area. Below the tabs, there is a "Future Issues" section with a "Create Issue" button. A table with the following structure is shown:

Issue	Items
No Items	

The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with the following items:

- Submissions
- Issues**
- Announcements
- Settings
 - Journal
 - Website
 - Workflow
 - Distribution
 - Users & Roles
- Statistics
 - Articles
 - Editorial Activity
 - Users
 - Reports
- Tools

An "Activate Windows" watermark is visible in the bottom right corner of the browser window.

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3 Pharmademica

17. Persiapan artikel yang akan dipublish

The screenshot displays the Pharmademica OJS 3 interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: `jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/3`. The main content area is partially obscured by a modal dialog box titled "Send To Production".

The dialog box contains the following elements:

- Send Email:** Two radio button options:
 Send an email notification to the author(s): admin pharmademica
 Do not send an email notification
- Rich Text Editor:** A toolbar with icons for bold, italic, underline, link, unlink, code, undo, redo, image, and link. Below the toolbar, the text reads:
admin pharmademica:

The editing of your submission, "KADAR POLIFENOL TOTAL PADA TEH HIJAU (CAMELLIA SINENSIS) MENGGUNAKAN EKSTRAKSI MASERASI DENGAN PERBANDINGAN PELARUT ETANOL - AIR," is complete.
We are now sending it to production.

Submission URL:
- Attachments:** A button with a plus sign and the text "Select Library Files to attach".
- Buttons:** "Next: Select Files for Production" and "Cancel".

The background interface shows a sidebar with navigation options: Submissions, Issues, Announcements, Settings (Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles), Statistics (Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports), and Tools. The main area displays "Activity Log" and "Library" buttons, and a "Send To Production" button. Below this, there is a "Participants" section with an "Assign" button, listing "Journal editor" (Tri Danang Kurniawan) and "Author" (admin pharmademica).

Aplikasi dalam OJS 3

18. Artikel telah selesai di publish

The screenshot displays the OJS 3 interface for a journal article. The browser address bar shows the URL: jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/workflow/index/1/3. The page title is "Pharmademica". The article title is "KADAR POLIFENOL TOTAL PADA TEH HIJAU (CAMELLIA SINENSIS) MENGGUNAKAN EKSTRAKSI MASERASI DEN". The article is currently in the "Production" stage of the workflow.

The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options: Submissions, Issues, Announcements, Settings (Journal, Website, Workflow, Distribution, Users & Roles), Statistics (Articles, Editorial Activity, Users, Reports), and Tools. The main content area shows the "Production" stage with tabs for "Submission", "Review", "Copyediting", and "Production".

Key features visible include:

- Production Ready Files:** A section with a search bar and an "Upload File" button. It currently shows "No Files".
- Production Discussions:** A section with an "Add discussion" button. It currently shows "No Items".
- Schedule For Publication:** A prominent blue button.
- Participants:** A section with an "Assign" button, listing the "Journal editor" (Tri Danang Kurniawan) and the "Author" (admin pharmademica).

The footer of the page contains the URL: [https://jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/\\$\\$\\$call\\$\\$\\$tab/workflow/workflow-tab/fetch-tab?submissionId=1&stageId=5](https://jurnal.poltekkespim.ac.id/index.php/pharmademica/$$$call$$$tab/workflow/workflow-tab/fetch-tab?submissionId=1&stageId=5).

감사합니다 Natick

Grazie

Danke

Ευχαριστίες

Dalu

Thank You

Köszönöm

Tack

Спасибо

Dank

Gracias

谢谢

Merci

Seé

ありがとう

Obrigado